

On Specific Salt Effects in the Racemisation and Aquation Reactions of the Trisoxalatochromium(III) Anion.

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The presence of rapidly formed ion pairs has been confirmed in mixtures of the trisoxalatochromate (III) anion and salts of divalent metallic cations by conductometric methods. Formation constants are of the order of 10^3 . Racemisation and aquation rate constants show linear dependence on $[M^{2+}]$ indicating that ion pairing is not a significant step in the racemisation or aquation reaction sequences. This conclusion is reinforced by rate studies using mixed cationic catalysis where additivity rather than competition is observed between the effects of two catalysis.

Acceleration of racemisation produced by divalent metal ions is shown to be due to entropy effects rather than enthalpy effects, and a model for this reaction involving a specifically oriented aquation sheath about the metallic cation is proposed.

BEESE and Johnson¹ first reported that metal ions catalyse the racemisation of the tris-oxalato chromium(III) anion, $Cr(Ox)_3^{3-}$. They found trivalent cations to be more effective than divalent ones and monovalent cations to be ineffective. A wide variation in the effectiveness of divalent ions was noted with Cu^{2+} being most effective. An early investigation² showed us that the order of catalytic effectiveness is

This is the same as the Irving-Williams order³ of stabilities of coordination compounds and this result drew attention to the importance of coordination of the catalytic ion in mediating this reaction.

Coordination of cationic catalysis to substrate is often invoked as a first step in metal ion mediated reactions and a search for such an association led Agget to show⁴, by solvent extraction methods, that an ion pair is formed between Cu^{2+} and $CrOx_3^{3-}$ with a formation constant of approximately 330 at room temperature.

Mechanisms for catalysed racemisation^{5,6} have utilised this "ion pairing" and the suggestion made that the rate determining step for racemisation is preceded by the rapid formation of a "complex" in which the metal ion bridges across the two oxygen atoms of the coordinated oxalate group and inductively weakens the bonds joining Cr to O

Aquation of the $Cr(Ox)_3^{3-}$ to form the bisoxalato diaquo derivative is also known⁷ to be effectively catalysed by divalent metal ions notably Cu^{2+} .

Cis-trans isomerisation of diaquo bisoxalato chromium(III) is also catalysed⁸ by divalent metallic cations the order of catalytic effectiveness being in agreement with the Irving-Williams order.

Discussion

The presence of the ion pair $Cu^{2+} \dots CuOx_3^{3-}$ with formation constant of about 300 has been confirmed by conductance measurements and this apparently lends support to the mechanism^{5,6} involving a rapidly formed ion pair in a step preceding the rate determining step as in Reaction Scheme I.

Reaction Scheme I

An immediate difficulty for this mechanism is that the plot of k_{obs} against $[Cu^{2+}]$ should be curved tending to a limiting value at high copper concentrations. The dashed curve in Fig. 1 shows the type of curve expected for an ion pair formation constant of 300. In contrast, the observed plot (Fig. 1) is strictly linear and Reaction Scheme I is ruled out if the formation constant is of the order of 300.

Further evidence on the importance of the ion pair as a reaction intermediate was sought in experiments using mixed catalytic salts. While 0.025 mol. l^{-1} Cu^{2+} accelerates the racemisation some 10-fold the same concentration of Mn^{2+} accelerates it only 2-fold. Furthermore the formation constants for $Cu^{2+} \dots CrOx_3^{3-}$

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Fig. 1. Dependence of rate of racemisation of $(CrOx_3)^{3-}$ on catalysing metal concentration. $[Na_2CrO_3] = 0.002 \text{ mol. l}^{-1}$, Temp = $0.1^\circ C$, pH = 4.3, ionic strength 1.0 mol. l^{-1} .

TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR RACEMISATION AND FOR AQUEOUS OF TRISOXALATOCHROMIUM (III) ANION AND FOR TRANS TO CIS ISOMERISATION OF BISOXALATOCHROMIUM (III) ANION IN THE PRESENCE OF MIXTURES OF BIVALENT METAL SALTS

Metal Ion (mol. l ⁻¹)	Ionic Str.	pH	t°C	$K_{obs} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Sum*
<i>Racemisation of $CrOx_3^{3-} \cdot 0.002 \text{ mol. l}^{-1}$</i>					
Cu ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	170	
Ni ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	86	
Cu ²⁺ 0.1 and Ni ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	257	256
Zn ²⁺ 0.025	1.0	3.5	24.3	100.5	
Mn ²⁺ 0.025	1.0	3.5	24.3	38.8	
Zn ²⁺ 0.025 and Mn ²⁺ 0.025	1.0	3.5	24.3	141	139.3
<i>Aqueous of $CrOx_3^{3-} \cdot 0.002 \text{ mol. l}^{-1}$</i>					
Cu ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	25	7.8	
Ni ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	25	0.32	
Mn ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	25	v. slow	
Cu ²⁺ 0.1 and Ni ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	25	8.6	8.2
Cu ²⁺ 0.1 and Mn ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	25	7.9	7.9

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR $M^{2+} \dots CrOx_3^{3-}$ ION PAIRS DETERMINED BY CONDUCTIVITY MEASUREMENTS AT $20^\circ C$

Concentration Mol. l ⁻¹	5×10^{-3}	1×10^{-2}	7×10^{-4}	5×10^{-4}	2×10^{-4}	1×10^{-4}	Mean
<i>Metal Ion</i>							
Mn ²⁺	21.4	197.3	262.9	305.5	382	—	234
Ni ²⁺	28	178	160	307	617	966	376
Cu ²⁺	35.5	221	176	307	—	893	326
Zn ²⁺	83	560	416	794	—	1406	651

Note:—Final conductivities were established within the time of mixing.

Considerable scatter is evident in these results and the formation constant shows a marked dependence on concentration. Mean values for all four metal ions studied, however, fall in the range 2 to 7 ($\times 10^3$).

TABLE 1 (CONTD)

Metal Ion (mol. l ⁻¹)	Ionic Str.	pH	t°C	$K_{obs} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Sum*
<i>Trans to Cis Isomerisation of $CrOx_2 \cdot 2H_2O \cdot 0.002 \text{ mol. l}^{-1}$</i>					
Cu ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	1.05	
Ni ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	0.59	
Mn ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	0.18	
Cu ²⁺ 0.1 and Ni ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	1.57	1.64
Cu ²⁺ 0.1 and Mn ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	1.22	1.23
Ni ²⁺ 0.1 and Mn ²⁺ 0.1	0.6	2.5	0.1	0.77	0.77

* "Sum" denotes the sum of rate constants in the presence of the separate metallic ions at the same ionic strength as that used for runs containing mixed metallic ions.

and $Mn^{2+} \dots CrOx_3^{3-}$ ion pairs are similar (263 and 209 respectively). It follows that, if Reaction Scheme I were followed, an experiment in which the reaction mixture contained both $0.025 \text{ mol. l}^{-1} Cu^{2+}$ and $0.025 \text{ mol. l}^{-1} Mn^{2+}$ there would be a competition for the limited amount of $CrOx_3^{3-}$ substrate and that the overall rate would approximate to the mean of those for Cu^{2+} and Mn^{2+} added separately. No such effect is seen, the rates being additive (at constant ionic strength) to a good degree of precision (Table 1). Similar activities and lack of competitive effects, between mixed catalytic ions are observed for aequation studies of $CrOx_3^{3-}$ and for studies of the trans to cis reaction of $CrOx_2 \cdot 2H_2O$. Details are also shown in Table 1.

We conclude that there is no kinetically significant formation of an ion pair between the substrate and the catalytic metallic cation occurring before the rate determining step.

How then does the catalytic cation mediate the reaction?

A model consistent with the kinetic data is that the attack of the metallic cation is the rate determining step.

The fact that the order of effectiveness of the metallic cations is the same as the Irving-Williams order has been invoked as evidence that the rate depends on the stability of the $CrOx_3^{3-} \dots M^{2+}$ ion pair. It is not strictly correct to use the Irving-Williams order in relation to such solvent separated ion pairs. Furthermore the formation constants as measured by conductivity methods (Table 2) show the $CrOx_3^{3-} \dots M^{2+}$ stabilities are all similar and do not lie in the Irving-Williams order for different choices of M^{2+} .

We suggest that the origin of the observed Irving-Williams order should be sought in the stability of the aquo complexes of the metallic cation. We propose that the rate determining step for racemisation of CrOx_3^{3-} in presence of a metallic cation be formulated as the attack of the cation bearing a correctly oriented sheath of water molecules. (The importance of water in the racemisation reaction has been stressed by several writers and we have shown⁶ that in aqueous-glycerol solutions the rate is proportional to $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2$. Its importance in aqution is obvious).

Fig. 2. Dependence of rate of aqution of $(\text{CrOx}_3)^{3-}$ on catalysing metal concentration. $[\text{K}_2\text{CrO}_7] = 0.002 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$, Ionic Strength = 1.0 mol l^{-1} , Temperature = 25°C, $\text{pH} = 7.5$

If the approach of a metallic cation bearing a correctly oriented water molecule sheath is to be proposed as the rate determining step for both racemisation and aqution, it becomes necessary to propose some distinction between these two reaction paths. Now aqution is much slower than racemisation in this system and we suggest that approach of an aquated cation to a close distance would be necessary to mediate aqution while a more distant approach would suffice to facilitate racemisation.

A likely consequence of this model would be that the energy of activation of cation catalysed racemisation would be independent of the cation chosen. Table 3 shows that activation energies are very nearly constant for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Na^+ and the same as that for racemisation without added salt. This result argues strongly against bond weakening through coordination to the substrate molecule. The origin of the acceleration on adding cations must therefore be sought in entropy effects. Such effects must also be responsible

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR RACEMISATION OF THE *Tris*-OXALATOCHROMIUM(III) ANION IN THE PRESENCE OF DIVALENT METALLIC CATIONS AT 298K

Cation and Concentration (Mol. l^{-1})	E_{act} (kJmol. $^{-1}$)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK $^{-1}$ mol. $^{-1}$
Cu^{2+} 0.025	68.2	-66.0
Ni^{2+} 0.025	68.2	-71.2
Zn^{2+} 0.025	63.6	-87.4
Mn^{2+} 0.025	67.8	-80.6
Ba^{2+} 0.025	63.9	-94.1
Na 1.0	68.2	-82.0
CrOx_3^{3-} (No added salt)	68.0	-86.6

for the Irving-Williams order seen for these cations in this reaction.

The more firmly bound water molecules of the aquo Cu^{2+} ion would be likely to be more stiffly oriented than those of Mn^{2+} , for example, and if this greater stiffness aided the racemisation process the effect would be evident as a contribution to the entropy of activation rather than to the enthalpy of activation.

It is interesting to compare the order of rates for the different cations with order of $\text{M}^{2+} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ stretching frequencies as determined by I.R. studies,⁹ on the sulphates. Details are in Table 4 and show that the mechanical rigidity of the bonds to water increases in the Irving-Williams order.

TABLE 4—STRETCHING FREQUENCIES FOR $\text{M}^{2+} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ BONDS IN SULPHATES IN CM^{-1}

Mg^{2+}	Mn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}
310	395	405	440	364

We postulate that when the CrOx_3^{3-} ion is racemised or aquated in the presence of polyvalent cations the rate determining step is the attack of the cation bearing correctly oriented water molecules. The tightness of binding of these water molecules is important and it is this effect which makes Cu^{2+} the most effective of the divalent metal catalysts.

The acceleration on adding divalent metallic cations is due to entropy effects rather than bond weakening effects. Although considerable ion pairing occurs (and is established within the time of mixing) between the divalent cation and the CrOx_3^{3-} substrate, this pairing has no effect on the rate of reaction.

Similar considerations probably apply to the catalysis of the cis-trans isomerisation of the $\text{CrOX}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}^-$ anion.

Experimental

Sodium trisoxalatochromium(III) and *trans* sodium bisoxalatochromium(III) were prepared and analysed by standard methods. Other salts used were of A. R. grade.

Absorption spectra were obtained on a Cary (Model 14) recording spectrophotometer which was also used for measuring aquation rates at 420 n.m. and 570 n.m.

Isomerisation rates for *trans*-bisoxalatodiaquo chromium (III) were followed at 416 n.m.

Conductivity measurements were made using a Philips P.R.500 resistance bridge in conjunction with a Philips P. W. 9510 conductivity cell. Formation constants for $\text{CrOx}_3^- \dots \text{M}^{2+}$ ion pairs were calculated using a modification of a method described by Dole⁹ for obtaining the dissociation constant of acetic acid. The degree of dissociation, X, is found thus :

$$X = \frac{\bar{\lambda}_{\text{expected}} - \bar{\lambda}_{\text{observed}}}{\bar{\lambda}_X}$$

where $\bar{\lambda}_{\text{expected}}$ is molar conductivity expected on mixing equal volumes of equimolar metal ion and CrOx_3^- solutions. This may be obtained by adding the molar conductivities of the individual solutions after making a correction for different ionic strength.

$\bar{\lambda}_{\text{observed}}$ is the measured molar conductivity on mixing the two solutions.

$\bar{\lambda}_X$ is a constant varying only with the charge on the ions and for M^{2+} cations and CrOx_3^- , the relevant value is 270¹⁰.

Formation constant, K, is calculated from

$$K = \frac{X}{C(1-X)^2} \text{ where } C \text{ is the concentration.}$$

Results are in Table 2.

Racemisation rates were measured using a Shimadzu QR-50 spectrophotometer with a polarimeter attachment using procedures already described¹¹.

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